

MESOSCALE MODELLING OF THE WEATHER ABOVE TITAN'S LAKES

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The Cassini-Huygens mission to the Saturn system played a major role in characterizing Saturn's largest moon Titan, where a massive nitrogen atmosphere holds ~ 5% of methane at temperatures that support a methane 'hydrological' cycle. Cassini revealed the presence of methane lakes and seas, clouds and riverbeds, and evidences of heavy rainfall. However, after the termination of the mission, many questions remain about the surface methane reservoirs and their connection to clouds and precipitation.

To better understand the methane cycle on Titan's surface, we investigate physical processes with a mesoscale climate model. Our research focuses on the effects of evaporation above methane lakes, providing insights into the quantity of evaporated methane, its transport by local winds, and the later effects on the atmosphere. This investigation began with a 2D version of the mtWRF atmospheric model (Rafkin & Soto, 2020) that showed that the canonical circulation over a methane lake on Titan is a lake breeze blowing at the surface from the cold lake to the warmer land driven by latent heat when methane evaporates. We then added heating/cooling by solar and infrared radiation in the model (Chatain et al., 2022) and observed strong diurnal and seasonal variations in the intensity and propagation of the lake breeze, which also affect the methane evaporation and the lake temperature.

More recently, we have added a third spatial dimension to the model. This improvement creates significant differences in how the simulated circulation preserves mass-continuity compared to 2D. Due to divergence of the air mass moving away from the lake at the surface, the lake breeze extends less over land in 3D. In contrast, due to convergence of the air mass at altitude, the subsidence over the lake is twice as strong in 3D. In addition, 3D simulations performed with a background wind lead to the formation of a pocket of strongly accelerated wind behind the lake, which was not observed in 2D simulations. We also investigated the effect of irregular shorelines for realistic lakes, compared to the idealized circular lakes. Over the realistic lake, surface wind and evaporation rate are enhanced in inlets, and decreased around peninsulas. At a few hundred meters in altitude, stronger winds form over the land on peninsulas. Simulations with several lakes show interactions between the lake's breezes, leading to resulting circulations that are complex and difficult to predict in the absence of 3D modelling. Winds and humidity increase with the size of the lake, reaching near-saturation values for the largest ones.

We conclude that even though they are computationally more expensive, 3D simulations are necessary to get accurate values for the winds and evaporation rates of Titan's lakes, and therefore to improve our understanding of Titan's methanological cycle.

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